

THE ROLE OF PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN CHILDREN'S LANGUAGE LEARNING.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11171855>

Abstract.

This article is about parental involvement in foreign language learning process and explore the parents' behavior and their perceptions in their children's English language learning. Moreover, benefits of parental involvement in children's life.

Key words: Parents' involvement, literacy, language development.

Introduction

In the realm of second language learning parental involvement plays a crucial role in facilitating the acquisition and development of language skills in children. The level of and quality of parental involvement can greatly influence a child's motivation, progress and success in learning a new language. Parental involvement plays a crucial role in children's language learning. Parents are a child's first and most important teachers, and they can greatly influence their child's language development by creating a language-rich environment at home. When parents actively engage with their children in conversations, read to them, and encourage them to explore and ask questions, they are helping to stimulate their child's language skills. Through regular interactions and feedback, parents can help their children expand their vocabulary, improve their grammar and syntax, and develop their communication skills. Furthermore, parents who speak multiple languages can also play a significant role in promoting multilingualism in their children. By exposing their children to different languages from a young age, parents can help them become proficient in multiple languages and enhance their cognitive abilities. In addition, parental involvement in children's language learning can also extend beyond the home environment. Parents can work collaboratively with teachers and other professionals to support their child's language development in school and other educational settings. By staying informed about their child's progress, communicating with teachers, and participating in school activities, parents can ensure that their child receives the necessary support to excel in language

learning. Overall, parental involvement is essential for children's language learning and development. By promoting a language-rich environment, supporting multilingualism, and collaborating with educators, parents can help their children become proficient communicators and succeed academically.

Literature review.

Several researches had been done before, in order to clarify whether parents' role in language learning is important or not. According to the Walberg (2011), parental behaviors appear to influence the children. Children with high parents' involvement perform better in school, such as get better grades, get higher score on tests, have better attendance and positive attitudes about school and homework.

Moreover, E. N. Patrikakou (2008) defines that parental involvement is a crucial force in children's development, learning and success at school and in life.

Forms of parental involvement suggested by Castro et al (2015) include monitoring activities, setting high expectations, maintaining lines of communication, and encouraging children to read daily. Tan et al (2020) identified six factors that they found to have a positive impact on student performance. These were: "parental wishes, parental support in raising their children, discussions between parents and children about school problems, parents' participation in school management and activities, reading books with parents, and empowering parents."

Chen et al. They stated that parents with low socioeconomic status may not have access to the language and may devote less time to their children learning the language. They describe high-income parents as "too greedy" about teaching their children languages.

Methods.

The subjects of this study were 4th grade students in University in Bukhara. To answer the questions, students were interviewed as the main data collection technique. The interview was done in the form of one on one interview every student was interviewed. They were asked about the advantages and drawbacks of their parents' involvement during their second language learning process.

In order to have an overall understanding of data indications, a quantitative analysis was carried out.

Discussion.

From the data, it is indicated that there are 2 type of students which are positive and negative. 13 out of 17 students owned positive perception toward English

language learning while the remaining number of students have negative attitude towards their parents' involvement to English language learning.

There are several common backgrounds. Students who have positive feeling said that if their parents' ask their everyday grades, how their teachers and peers behave them, it will increase their learning process and give them motivation to study more. In contrast, students who have negative attitude towards their parents' involvement to their study have said that if their parents always ask about their grades, they feel uncomfortable and it disturbs their study. They said it is not necessary to involve parents to the second language learning process.

The parents' reflections and existing literature support the notion that the challenges can be addressed in various ways. Generally, some parents use extrinsic motivators such as reward and punishment, while other parents believe in encouragement and having dialogues with their children. In fact, empathizing parents can have a significant impact on shaping learning experiences that resonate with their children's personal preferences and motivations (Kohlhoff & Barnett, 2013).

In conclusion, it is certain that not all people want to involve their parents to language learning process.

Conclusion.

One of the key ways parents can support their child's language learning is through engaging in meaningful conversations. By talking to their children regularly and encouraging communication, parents can help children practice and improve their language skills. This can involve asking open-ended questions, discussing various topics, and actively listening to their child's thoughts and ideas. Through these interactions, children not only expand their vocabulary but also learn important communication techniques and social skills. Reading with children is another powerful way parents can enhance their child's language development. Reading books to children exposes them to new words, concepts, and narratives, helping to broaden their understanding of language and literacy. Parents can also encourage children to ask questions, make predictions about the story, and engage in discussions about the characters or themes in the book. This not only boosts language skills but also fosters a love for reading and learning.

In addition to conversations and reading, parents can support their child's language learning by exposing them to different forms of language use. This can include music, rhymes, and storytelling, which help children develop their language skills in a fun and engaging way. Parents can also provide

opportunities for their children to practice writing, speaking, and listening in various contexts, such as through games, role-playing, and creative activities.

It is important for parents to adapt their approaches to language learning based on their child's age, interests, and level of development. Younger children may benefit from simple and repetitive language activities, while older children may be ready for more advanced conversations and language challenges. By understanding their child's unique needs and abilities, parents can tailor their support to help their child progress and succeed in their language learning journey.

In conclusion, parental involvement in children's language learning is essential for fostering strong communication skills, vocabulary, and cognitive abilities. By actively engaging in conversations, reading with their child, and providing diverse language experiences, parents can play a critical role in helping their child develop a love for language and communication that will benefit them throughout their lives.

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